

Arrangements, $P(e_i)P(e_j) = P(e_k)$ and the Maxwell-Boltzmann and Power Law Distributions

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In the statistics of the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution, one makes use of the idea of elastic collisions and the conservation of energy. Thus, when one maximizes entropy, it is subject to a physical constraint, namely the average energy present. In previous notes, we argued that the main idea behind the MB distribution is: $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3=e_1+e_2)$. In this relation, one sees the explicit notion of energy being distributed i.e. $e_1+e_2=e_3$. The relation shows that one cannot distinguish between products of probabilities representing the same total energy. This leads to the idea of maximizing the number of arrangements of distributing energy, because all have the same probability.

In this note, we argue that there seems to be a more general statistical idea at work which is concerned with probabilities more than with the case of energy conservation. In the MB case, the two happen to coincide. In particular, we suggest that one examine: $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$ with e_1+e_2 not equal e_3 . One must then find a relationship between e_1, e_2 and e_3 . In other words, a given e_1 and e_2 map to a value e_3 such that $P(e_3)$ has the same probability as $P(e_1)P(e_2)$. Given that one may take the logarithm of $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$, this leads to a conservation law as well the form $\ln(P(e_i)) = \text{function}(e_i)$. $\ln(P)$ appears in Stirling's relation: $\ln(N!) \approx N \ln(N)$ for N large, so one may consider $d/dP \{ P \ln(P) \} = \ln(P) + \text{Constant}$ as being the maximization of the number of arrangements linked with $\text{function}(e_i)$. This function is only e_i/T for the MB case. Thus one maximizes subject to an constraint: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ function}(e_i) P(e_i)$ which is a mathematical object which accounts for "equal probabilities" i.e. $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$. This does not imply that $P \ln(P)$ is entropy because a different recipe is used for this quantity, namely: $dS/dP = a+be_i$. In other words, entropy maximization is associated with the constraint $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i P(e_i)$. We apply these ideas to the power law: $(1-ke/T)$ (power $1/k$) which appears in (1).

The Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution and the Distribution of Energy

The MB distribution may derived by considering two body elastic scattering such that there is time reversal balance i.e.

$$E_1+E_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{and} \quad P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)P(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

Taking \ln of ((1b)) and equating with ((1a)), multiplied by a constant, yields the MB distribution (unnormalized): $\exp(-e/T)$ which may then be normalized.

In ((1a)) and ((1b)), if one considers $e_4=0$, then: $e_1+e_2 = e_3$ and $P(e_1)P(e_2)= P(e_3)$ ((2)) if $P(e_4)=1$ which it does (unnormalized probability). One may see, however, that $e_1+e_2=e_3$ means that energy is being distributed i.e. is conserved and that this keeps the product of probabilities $P(e_1)P(e_2)$ equivalent to $P(e_3)$. Thus the main statistical idea, we argue, is to find a probability equivalent to a product probability. This happens to coincide with conservation of energy in the MB case, i.e. with an e_3 which satisfies $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)$ such that $e_3=e_1+e_2$. This means

any distribution of a total energy among N particles has the same probability. One may physically calculate the number of arrangements of energy E among N particles in such a case. If one relaxes the total E constraint and replaces it with an average $E_{ave} = \sum_i e_i P(e_i)$, then the number of arrangements is:

$$N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)! \quad \text{Where } n(e_i) = NP(e_i) \quad ((3))$$

Taking Ln of ((3)) and maximizing with respect to the constraint $\sum_i e_i P(e_i)$ yields the MB distribution. This is of course identical to $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_1+e_2)$, but in this case, physical arrangements actually exist.

The question we ask is: What happens if $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)$, but $e_1+e_2 \neq e_3$? We examine this situation in the context of the Power Law distribution.

Power Law Distribution and $P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3)$

We consider the Power Law distribution given in (1) i.e.:

$$P(e_i/T) = C (1 - ke_i/T)^{1/k} \quad ((4))$$

One sometimes sees the Power Law distribution: $P(e_i/T) = C (e_i/T)^{-1/k}$ ((5)) (from (2)), but in this case, T may be absorbed in the normalization and so T (temperature) disappears unless one links it to k or the bounds on e. We also note that $P(e=0) = 1$ for $C=1$ in ((4)) i.e. the unnormalized probability.

In the power law case:

$$P(e_1)P(e_2) = P(e_3), \text{ but } e_1+e_2 \neq e_3 \quad ((6))$$

$$\text{In fact: } 1/k \ln(1 - ke_1/T) + 1/k \ln(1 - ke_2/T) = 1/k \ln(1 - ke_3/T) \quad ((7))$$

The $1/k$ factor disappears and one may combine k/T into one parameter.

As an aside, we first ask how one may measure k/T in such a situation. It is possible to measure the number of particles with a certain energy e. Thus one may find:

$$P(e_1)/P(e_2) = b_1/b_2 \quad \text{or} \quad \ln(P(e_1)) - \ln(P(e_2)) = \ln(b_1/b_2) = \text{experimental number}$$

If one has two sets, i.e. e_1, e_2 and e_3, e_4 , then:

$$\{\ln(P(e_1)) - \ln(P(e_2))\} / \{\ln(P(e_3)) - \ln(P(e_4))\} = \ln(b_1/b_2) / \ln(b_3/b_4) \quad ((8))$$

The RHS of ((8)) is an experimental number and $1/k$ from the power disappears in the ratio. The LHS side of ((8)) is a function of the single parameter k/T and one may use ((8)) to solve for it numerically. With k/T known, one may find $1/k$.

((7)) shows that in order to conserve probability, probabilities associated with e_1 and e_2 are not equivalent (in a product sense) to a probability associated with $e_3=e_1+e_2$. Thus the main idea in statistics is conservation of probability, not energy. In the MB case, it happens that conservation of probability is associated with conservation of energy i.e. $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$ means $e_1+e_2=e_3$. The power law example shows that this is not always the case.

What about arrangements in the Power Law case? ((6)) or \ln of it shows that $\ln(P)$ (information in information theory) appears, but this is also part of Stirling's approximation:

$$\ln(N!) \approx N \ln(N) \text{ for } N \text{ large } ((9))$$

One may thus argue mathematically that one may maximize arrangements of energy E among N particles (relaxing the constraint on a fixed E) subject to the constraint:

$$\sum_i \ln(1-ke_i/T) P(e_i) \text{ where } P(e_i) \text{ is an unnormalized probability } ((10))$$

This formally yields the power law distribution with $1/k$ appearing as a Lagrange multiplier. We argue that one really considers equal probability scenarios and these do not involve the simple distribution of E among particles in any way with the same probability. One must respect $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$ with the constraint ((7)). Thus the main idea is equal probability scenarios, not energy conservation.

Given that $N \ln(N)$ appears in the maximization of arrangements, one may ask: Is $-P \ln(P)$ the entropy in the Power Law case as it is in the MB case? We argue that it is not because entropy is defined through:

$$dS/dP = (1-ke/T) \quad ((11))$$

Thus entropy may be found using the recipe:

((A)) Write $(1-ke/T) = \text{Function}(P(e/T))$

((B)) Integrate $\text{Function}(P)$ with respect to dP so that d/dP returns $1-ke/T$.

This implies that $\sum_i (1-ke_i/T) P(e_i)$ is used as a constraint. This is a physical constraint associated with average energy and $\sum_i P(e_i)=1$. Thus, we argue that the notion of entropy is associated with the physical constraint on average energy, but that the power law distribution itself (and the idea of the maximization of arrangements with a nonaverage energy constraint) is a different approach and is linked with $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$ where $e_1+e_2 \neq e_3$.

Thus entropy (and its maximization subject to energy conservation) and the maximization of arrangements (subject to a constraint which makes $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$) are different in the Power Law case, but the same in the MB case.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$ is associated with conservation of energy $e_1+e_2=e_3$. This is why elastic scattering is associated with the MB scenario. This means that physically any distribution of a total energy E among N particles has the same probability. Total energy conservation is a natural constraint in a physical system, so one has the idea of different arrangements with the same probability and energy conservation together. One may relax the total energy constraint and use the constraint $E_{ave} = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i P(e_i)$. As a result, one may maximize the \ln of the number of arrangements and call this function entropy.

Is this always the case? We argue that it is not and that the main statistical idea is found in: $P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)$. In other words, one is interested in equal probability which does not necessarily mean energy conservation i.e. e_1+e_2 may not be equal to e_3 , but the product probabilities equal $P(e_3)$. Thus in terms of arrangements, if $P(e=0)$ unnormalized is 1 as in the power law $P(e)=C (1-ke/T)^{1/k}$, then an arrangement of a one particle with e_1 and one particle with e_2 is equivalent (in terms of probability) to one particle with $e=0$ and the other with e_3 . Energy is not conserved in this picture of equal probability arrangements. Nevertheless one may use $\ln(P(e_1))+ \ln(P(e_2)) = \ln(P(e_3))$ together with a suitable conservation law: $1/k \ln(1-e_1k/T) + 1/k \ln(1-e_2k/T) = 1/k \ln(1-e_3k/T)$ and mathematically establish a maximization of $\ln(\text{arrangements})$ using Stirling's approximation and the constraint: $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } P(e_i) \ln(1-e_1k/T)$. This is no longer a constraint on the average energy i.e. a natural physical constraint. In such a case, the $\ln(\text{arrangements})$ yields $-P \ln(P)$, but this is not entropy (it is the \ln of the number of arrangements keeping probability the same). Entropy is associated with the physical constraint $E_{ave} = \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i P(e_i)$ so: $dS/dP = 1-ke/T$. (The constraint $\text{Sum over } i \text{ } P(e_i) = 1$ is also included).

Thus maximization of entropy and maximization of $\ln(\text{arrangements})$ are different and use different constraints, but both yield the Power Law distribution.

References

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